

Supplemental materials

Table S1

Table S1. Mechanical and geometrical properties of 237 experimental data of steel beam-to-column connections.

Researcher	Year	Specimen ID	Beam Section	h/t_w	L/d	$b_p/2t_f$	L/r_y (λ_y)	L/r_x (λ_x)	F_y (Mpa)	Connection type	Seismic Classification		
Popov and Stephen[1]	1970	EERC-70-3-Specimen1	W18x50	48	9	42	101	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-70-3-Specimen2	W18x50	48	9	42	101	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-70-3-Specimen3	W18x50	48	9	42	101	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-70-3-Specimen4	W18x50	48	9	42	101	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-70-3-Specimen5	W24x76	51	7	41	87	17	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-70-3-Specimen6	W24x76	51	7	41	87	17	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
Tsai[2]	1987	EERC-70-3-Specimen8	W18x50	48	9	42	101	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		2	W18X40	54	7	38	103	18	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		3	W18X35	56	7	40	106	125	248	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		4	W18X40	54	7	38	103	18	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		UCB-EERC-88-19-8811-Specimen1	W18x40	54	7	38	103	18	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		UCB-EERC-88-19-8811-Specimen7	W21x44	53	6	35	102	16	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
Ghobarah et al.[3]	1992	UCB-EERC-88-19-8811-Specimen11	W21x44	53	6	35	102	16	248	BUEP	Pre-Northridge		
		18	W21X44	42	12	44	108	28	303	BEEP	Pre-Northridge		
		CB1	W14x38	49	11	46	108	25	303	BEEP	Pre-Northridge		
		CC1	W16x40	54	7	38	109	19	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		Engelhardt and Sabol [4]	1994	1B	W36x150	54	7	38	109	19	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
				2B	W36x150	54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Post-Northridge
3B	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Post-Northridge		
5A	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Post-Northridge		
5B	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WSEP	Post-Northridge		
6A	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WSEP	Post-Northridge		
6B	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Post-Northridge		
7A	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Post-Northridge		
7B	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Post-Northridge		
8A	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Post-Northridge		
8B	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WSPFF	Post-Northridge		
9A	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WSPFF	Post-Northridge		
Uang and Latham[5]	1995	9B	W36x150	54	7	38	107	18	248	MNHSMTFTM	Post-Northridge		
		MNH-SMRF-95-03-Specimen1	W36x150	54	7	38	107	18	248	MNHSMTFTM	Post-Northridge		
		MNH-SMRF-95-03-Specimen2	W36x150	54	7	38	107	18	248	MNHSMTFTM	Post-Northridge		
		MNH-SMRF-95-03-Specimen3	W36x150	50	7	35	104	18	345	MNHSMTFTM	Post-Northridge		
Allen et al.[6]	1996	MNH-SMRF-95-03-Specimen4	W36x170	35	7	25	105	19	351	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-1	W36X256	27	5	28	53	13	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-2	W36x393	27	5	28	53	13	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-3	W36x393	27	6	28	55	14	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
Engelhardt et al.[7]	1996	SSDA-3A	W36x393	54	6	38	94	16	250	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-5	W36X150	44	7	32	99	17	250	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-6	W36X194	50	6	35	92	16	250	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-7	W36X170	38	8	37	79	20	250	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-8	W36X280	38	8	37	79	20	250	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		SSDA-9	W36X280	54	3	38	48	8	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		UTDB1	W36x160	45	3	32	47	8	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		UTDB2	W36x194	49	8	35	111	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		UTDB3	W36x170	54	8	38	115	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		UTDB4	W36x150	45	9	34	124	23	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		UTDB5	W30x148	54	7	38	109	19	248	BH-WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		Shuey[8]	1996	UTA-1R	W36x150	54	7	38	109	19	248	BH-WFP	Pre-Northridge
UTA-1RB	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
UTA-2R	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	H-WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
UTA-3R	W36x150			54	7	38	109	19	248	WFP	Pre-Northridge		
UTA-4	W36x150			49	14	46	146	34	248	H-BF-B	Post-Northridge		
R1	W36X150			49	14	46	141	33	248	H-BF-B	Post-Northridge		
Hodgson[9]	1996	R2	W36X150	54	6	38	90	15	248	BH-BF-B	Post-Northridge		
		HH1	W16X40	54	6	38	90	15	248	H-BF-B	Post-Northridge		
		HH2	W16X40	54	10	40	135	24	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		WH2	W36X150	54	8	38	114	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
Iwankiw and Carter[10]	1996	HH3	W36X150	54	7	38	100	17	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		DBT1A-19604	W30x99	47	7	34	98	18	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		DBT2A-19604	W36x150	57	7	40	103	18	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
Herrick[11]	1996	DBT2B-19604	W36x150	52	9	41	116	22	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		SESB1-HSE9702	W33x169	57	7	40	103	18	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		SESB2-HSE9702	W36x135	54	7	38	108	19	272	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SESB3-HSE9702	W27x94	54	7	38	108	19	272	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
Zekioglu et al.[12]	1996	SESB4-HSE9702	W36x135	56	6	37	100	16	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		NIST98-ARUP1	W36x150	34	10	38	83	23	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		NIST98-COH1	W27x178	50	8	37	109	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		NIST98-COH3	W33x152	50	7	37	100	18	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		NIST98-COH4	W33x152	50	7	37	100	18	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		NIST98-COH5	W33x153	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
Uang and Bondad[13]	1996	SSRP-96-02-SpecimenUCSD-1R	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SSRP-96-02-SpecimenUCSD-2R	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SSRP-96-02-SpecimenUCSD-3R	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SSRP-96-02-SpecimenUCSD-6	W30x99	54	6	38	90	16	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		NIST-2C	W36x150	56	5	41	70	13	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		

Researcher	Year	Specimen ID	Beam Section	h/t_w	L/d	$b_f/2t_f$	L/r_y (λ_y)	L/r_x (λ_x)	F_y (Mpa)	Connection type	Seismic Classification		
Popov et al.[14]	1997	P9704-DASSE1	W33x130	56	5	41	70	13	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		P9704-DASSE2	W33x130	45	7	32	96	17	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		P9704-DASSE3	W36x194	45	7	32	96	17	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		P9704-DASSE4	W36x194	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
FEMA-289[15]	1997	EERC-AN1	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-PN1	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-PN2	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-PN3	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		EERC-RN1A	W30x99	54	7	38	109	19	345	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		UCB-PN1	W36x150	54	7	38	109	19	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		UCB-PN3	W36x150	54	7	38	109	19	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		UCB-RN3	W36x150	54	10	40	135	24	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		UCSD-2	W30x99	54	10	40	135	24	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		UCSD-3	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	248	WUF-B	Pre-Northridge		
		UTA-4	W30x99	46	13	42	306	32	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
Nakashima et al.[16]	1998	JSE-1998-SB6Z3F-Ky3D	WF600x250x1	46	13	42	306	32	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		JSE-1998-SB6A7F-Ky1	WF600x250x1	54	5	38	70	12	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
Popov et al.[17]	1998	P9602-UCBDB1	W36x135	47	11	40	276	28	248	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
Suiza et al.[18]		N2	WF500x200x1	47	11	40	276	28	248	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		N4	WF500x200x1	47	11	40	276	28	248	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		N5	WF500x200x1	47	11	40	276	28	248	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		N6	WF500x200x1	47	11	40	276	28	248	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		ND	WF500x200x1	26	20	58	79	46	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		R2	RHS 350 x 350	26	23	58	91	53	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		R3	RHS 350 x 350	26	23	58	91	53	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		R5	RHS 350 x 350	26	23	58	91	53	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		RD	RHS 350 x 350	55	11	43	144	28	334	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		Lee et al.[19]	1999	LEE 1-1	W24X68	55	11	43	144	28	334	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
				LEE 1-2	W24X68	55	11	43	144	28	317	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
				LEE 3-1	W24X68	55	11	43	144	28	317	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
				LEE 3-2	W24X68	54	9	40	129	23	297	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
LEE 4-2	W30X99			54	9	40	128	23	357	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
LEE 5-1	W30X99			54	9	40	128	23	297	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
LEE 5-2	W30X99			54	9	40	128	23	348	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
LEE 6-1	W30X99			54	9	40	128	23	285	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
LEE 6-2	W30X99			54	8	38	109	19	292	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
LEE 7-1	W36X150			54	8	38	109	19	292	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
LEE 7-2	W36X150			55	14	43	180	35	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
Murray and Sumner [20]	1999	4E-125-15-24	W24x68	55	14	43	180	35	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4E-125-1125-24	W24x68	55	26	43	333	65	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4E-125-1375-24	W24x68	55	26	43	333	65	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4E-125-1375-24-N	W24x68	55	26	43	333	65	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4E-125-1375-24-S	W24x68	54	21	40	298	53	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4W-125-1-30	W30x99	54	21	40	298	53	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4W-125-125-36	W30x99	54	21	40	298	53	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4W-125-1125-30	W30x99	54	17	38	253	44	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		4W-125-1375-36	W36x150	54	21	40	298	53	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		8ES-125-1-30	W30x99	54	17	38	253	44	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		8ES-125-25-36	W36x150	54	17	38	253	44	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		8ES-125-125-36	W36x150	54	21	40	298	53	345	BUEP	Post-Northridge		
		8ES-125-175-30	W30x99	52	10	41	133	26	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
Choi[21]	2000	S-8-2	W24x68	57	8	42	118	21	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		S-9-1	W30x99	57	8	42	118	21	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		S-9-2	W30x99	50	8	37	111	20	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		S-10-1	W30x124	50	8	37	111	20	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		S-10-2	W30x124	54	8	38	115	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		Engelhardt et al.[22]	2000	DBBWC-N	W36x150	54	8	38	115	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
DBBWWPZ-N	W36x150	54	8	38	115	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge				
DBBWWPZC-N	W36x150	54	8	38	115	20	248	RBS	Pre-Northridge				
DBBWWPZC-S	W36x150	54	8	38	115	20	248	RBS	Pre-Northridge				
DBBWWPZ-S	W36x150	50	7	37	101	18	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge				
SSDA Associates[23]	2000	17	W33x141	51	9	40	116	22	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		19	W27x94	51	9	40	116	22	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		20	W27x94	36	7	35	64	16	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		21	W36x300	36	7	35	64	16	345	SSDA	Post-Northridge		
		22	W36x300	54	9	38	136	23	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
Ricles et al.[24]	2000	SAC-BD-0024-C2L	W36x150	54	9	38	131	23	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SAC-BD-0024-C3L	W36x150	54	10	38	143	25	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SAC-BD-0024-C3R	W36x150	54	9	38	136	23	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SAC-BD-0024-C5L	W36x150	54	9	38	136	24	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		SAC-BD-0024-T1	W36x150	54	9	38	136	24	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		SAC-BD-0024-T2	W36x150	54	9	38	136	24	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
		SAC-BD-0024-T3	W36x150	54	9	38	136	24	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		SAC-BD-0024-T4	W36x150	54	9	38	136	24	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge		
SAC-BD-0024-T6	W36x150	54	9	40	128	23	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge				
Stojadinovic et al.[25]	2000	4*1	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		4*2	W30x100	54	9	40	128	23	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		
		5*1	W30x101	51	13	36	196	34	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
Tsai and Chen[26]	2000	RB1	H600X200X11	51	10	36	151	26	248	RBS	Post-Northridge		
		RB5	H600X200X11	57	8	42	117	21	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge		

Researcher	Year	Specimen ID	Beam Section	h/t_w	L/d	$b_f/2t_f$	L/r_y (λ_y)	L/r_x (λ_x)	F_y (Mpa)	Connection type	Seismic Classification
Uang et al.[27]	2000	SSR-00-LS-1	W30x99	57	8	42	117	21	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
		SSR-00-LS-4	W30x99	54	7	38	100	17	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
		SSRP-00-CW-1	W36x150	52	10	32	178	27	345	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
		SSRP-00-CW-2	W24x62	54	6	38	90	16	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
		SSRP-00-DC-1	W36x150	54	6	38	90	16	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
		SSRP-00-DC-2	W36x150	34	8	37	67	19	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
Kim et al.[28]	2000	PEER-0007-SpecimenRC01	W27x194	54	9	40	128	23	345	WFP	Post-Northridge
		PEER-0007-SpecimenRC02	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	345	WFP	Post-Northridge
		PEER-0007-SpecimenRC03	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	345	WFP	Post-Northridge
		PEER-0007-SpecimenRC04	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	345	WFP	Post-Northridge
		PEER-0007-SpecimenRC05	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	345	WFP	Post-Northridge
		PEER-0007-SpecimenRC06	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	345	WFP	Post-Northridge
		PEER-0007-SpecimenRC08	W30x99	54	9	40	128	23	345	WFP	Post-Northridge
		PEER-0007-SpecimenRC09	W30x99	55	12	43	147	29	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
Schneider and Teeraparbong[29]	2000	BFP01	W24x68	55	12	43	147	29	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		BFP02	W24x68	54	9	40	132	24	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		BFP03	W30x99	55	12	43	147	29	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		BFP04	W24x68	54	9	40	132	24	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		BFP05	W30x99	55	12	43	147	29	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		BFP06	W24x68	55	12	43	147	29	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		BFP07	W24x68	55	12	43	147	29	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		BFP08	W24x68	44	12	35	147	26	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
Lee et al.[30]	2002	CR1	W24X94	44	12	35	147	26	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		CR2	W24X94	44	12	35	147	26	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		CR3	W24X94	44	12	35	147	26	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		CR5	W24X94	52	10	41	125	24	344	BEP-MC	Pre-Northridge
Tort and Hajjar[31]	2003	S1-E	W27X95	52	10	41	125	24	344	BEP-MC	Pre-Northridge
		S2-W	W27X96	52	10	41	125	24	344	BEP-MC	Pre-Northridge
		S2-E	W27X97	52	10	41	125	24	344	BEP-MC	Pre-Northridge
		S3-W	W27X98	54	8	38	114	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
Ricles et al.[32]	2004	ATLSS0413-SPEC1-E	W36x150	54	8	38	115	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
		ATLSS0413-SPEC2-E	W36x150	54	8	38	115	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
		ATLSS0413-SPEC3-E	W36x150	54	8	38	114	20	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
		ATLSS0413-SPEC4-E	W36x150	50	9	37	131	24	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
		ATLSS0413-SPEC5-E	W30x108	50	9	37	128	23	345	RBS	Post-Northridge
		ATLSS0413-SPEC6-E	W30x108	52	9	32	162	24	248	WUB-B	Post-Northridge
Ricles et al.[33]	2004	JSE-2004-1	W24X62	52	9	32	162	24	248	T1	Post-Northridge
		JSE-2004-3	W24X62	52	9	32	162	24	248	MDST	Post-Northridge
		JSE-2004-4	W24X62	52	9	32	162	24	248	MDST	Post-Northridge
		JSE-2004-5	W24X62	52	9	32	162	24	248	TB	Post-Northridge
		JSE-2004-6	W24X62	56	17	37	279	44	345	T-Stub	Pre-Northridge
		FS3	W21X44	56	17	37	279	44	345	T-Stub	Pre-Northridge
Ocel et al.[34]	2004	FS4	W21X44	57	15	36	263	39	345	T-Stub	Pre-Northridge
		FS5	W24X55	57	15	36	263	39	345	T-Stub	Pre-Northridge
		FS6	W24X55	57	15	36	263	39	345	T-Stub	Pre-Northridge
		FS7	W24X55	57	15	36	263	39	345	T-Stub	Pre-Northridge
		FS8	W24X55	57	15	36	263	39	345	T-Stub	Pre-Northridge
		FS10	W24X55	50	10	46	106	25	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
		SW	H700x300x13x	50	9	46	92	21	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
		MW	H700x300x13x	50	9	46	95	22	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
		SB	H700x300x13x	50	9	46	95	22	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
		MB	H700x300x13x	51	14	36	200	34	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
Lee et al.[35]	2005	MW1	H600x200x11x	51	14	36	200	34	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
		MW2	H600x200x11x	51	14	36	200	34	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
		SW1	H600x200x11x	47	12	34	166	29	248	RBS	Post-Northridge
		SW2	H606x201x12x	44	12	32	156	29	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		b1f	W30x148	44	12	32	161	30	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		b2f	W30x148	43	13	37	146	31	240	TS-W-K	Post-Northridge
		TS100	H506X201X11	43	13	37	146	31	240	TS-W-K	Post-Northridge
		TS120	H506X201X11	43	13	37	146	31	240	TS-W-K	Post-Northridge
Shin et al.[37]	2008	TS140	H506X201X11	43	13	37	146	31	240	TS-W-K	Post-Northridge
		TSD100	H506X201X11	43	13	37	146	31	240	TS-W-K	Post-Northridge
		TSD120	H506X201X11	43	13	37	146	31	240	TS-W-K	Post-Northridge
		TSH100	H506X201X11	43	13	37	146	31	240	TS-W-K	Post-Northridge
		TSH120	H506X201X11	54	9	38	134	23	345	KBB	Pre-Northridge
		s1	W36x150	54	9	38	134	23	345	KBB	Pre-Northridge
		s2	W36x150	54	9	38	134	23	345	KBB	Pre-Northridge
		s3	W36x150	47	10	45	242	33	235	WFP	Post-Northridge
Kosarieh and Danesh [39]	2016	SN1	I400x180x8x12	47	10	45	242	33	235	WFP	Post-Northridge
		SN2	H400x180x8x1	52	12	39	166	30	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
Shin[40]	2017	UT01	W30x108	52	12	39	166	30	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		UT02	W30x108	54	10	38	144	25	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		UT04	W36x150	54	10	38	144	25	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		UT05	W36x150	54	10	38	144	25	345	BFP	Post-Northridge
		UT07	W36x150	57	15	36	266	39	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		UT08	W24x55	57	15	36	266	39	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		UT09	W24x55	57	15	36	266	39	345	WUF-W	Post-Northridge
		UT10	W24x55	53	9	43	112	22	370	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
		SRB-25	H800X300X26	53	9	43	112	22	370	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
		IRB-25	H800X300X26	53	9	43	112	22	370	WUF-B	Post-Northridge
Tsai et al.[41]	2020	SFB-26	H800X300X26	53.	9.3	42.9	112.0	22.5	370	WUF-B	Post-Northridge

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